

ON MODELING WORK EXPERIENCES AND THEIR INFLUENCING FACTORS AMONG EMPLOYEES IN A UNIVERSITY

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Favorable work experiences are vital in becoming efficient in functioning at a University. Henceforth, it is crucial to determine some factors that might improve the employees' work experiences. This study aims to develop statistical models to elucidate the various determinants of work experiences among employees at Visayas State University, Philippines. Secondary data were utilized consisting of the different work experiences and their possible determinants. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis were employed to summarize and predict influencing determinants of work experiences. Results revealed that working at a University is challenging. Regression models have shown that teaching is more logical compared to administrative work and male workers are more likely to enjoy their job compared to female employees. Moreover, income, fair administration, opportunities for promotion, and awards are positively influencing the employees' work experiences at the university. Furthermore, results revealed that overtime pay is a good remuneration that makes employees feel that their work is rewarding. Hence, to increase employees' satisfaction and improve their well-being, the university may provide incentives or benefits for their extra service. Recognition or awards may also be provided for the meritorious performance of employees to motivate them in doing their best.

Keywords: work experiences, determinants, multiple regression models, state university, Philippines

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1. INTRODUCTION

Work experience is about learning the job to gain and develop some ability. It can also increase productivity, effectiveness, and efficiency which is a great way to build skills (Kini & Podolsky, 2016; Rozgonjuk et al., 2020; Casinillo et al., 2021). In the study of Takeuchi et al. (2019), it is stated that work experience influences the performance of employees. On the other hand, dissatisfied workers result in inadequate performance, burnout, and stressful experiences (Juengst et al., 2019; Marcu, 2019). However, a worker with positive experiences is more possible to acquire new ideas that improve self-ability and efficacy (Casinillo et al., 2020). Vasta (2020), stated that work experiences vary depending on the demographic profile such as ethnicity, class, culture, and gender relations. Likewise, workers' experiences and well-being deviate as a function of commitment to work and conflict of interest in the workplace (Greenhaus et al., 1987). In that case, it is crucial to investigate the different work experiences of diverse employees to understand its nature and possible predictors. Indeed, elucidating the well-being of workers concerning work experience can be a basis for implementing some policy inputs in a workplace. For instance, the study of Casinillo and colleagues (2021) suggested that a University must focus on stress management and evaluate its work assignment to attain a good experience and productivity for its employees.

In the State University of Baybay City, Leyte, Philippines, namely, Visayas State University (VSU), some diverse employees contributed to the productivity of the Institution. The said University is serving in educating young minds in the locality of Baybay City as well as neighboring municipalities and provinces of Leyte. This University has a wide range of coverage and is composed of a large number of employees. Apparently, employees came from different places and backgrounds which perhaps a factor of various needs and work experiences. Senreich et al. (2020) and Toropova et al. (2021) initiated studies on job satisfaction in regard to working conditions and workers' characteristics. The study revealed that working environment and workloads are the most important factor in job satisfaction or positive work experiences. Likewise, in the study of Borman and Dowling (2008), dissatisfaction in the workplace or working environment is the main reason for employee turnover. In that case, work experiences must be examined to improve employees' well-being and job satisfaction. The outcome of investigating employees' work experiences may help reduce or minimize worker attrition and increase employee retention in a university. Work experiences such

as routinely, creative, challenging, enjoyable, logical, and rewarding are interesting to elucidate since they describe wholly the perception of workers in view of their subjective well-being and satisfaction (Casinillo & Casinillo, 2021). In regards to that, this study will apply the concept of the said work experiences to the employees in the university to capture its determinants that might be useful for human resource development.

Work experiences among employees are a very important constituent in improving an organization or institution. Hence, it is crucial to investigate the level of perception among employees in their experiences in working at a University to generate some management policies that favor their well-being and job satisfaction. Modeling the level of perception of different work experiences among employees in a State University has never been done. Moreover, studies on work experience in a University and its factors are a bit limited in the body of scientific knowledge. Thus, this study was initiated. Generally, the study dealt with evaluating the perception scores of different work experiences and their influencing determinants among employees in Visayas State University, Leyte, Philippines. Henceforth, the study has the following specific objectives: (1) to summarize the socio-demographic profile among employees; to measure the level of perception score of the different work experiences among employees; and (2) to construct regression models that capture the influencing factors of the different work experiences among employees. On the face of it, the scope of this study is to model the perception of VSU workers concerning their experiences in the time of the early COVID-19 pandemic setup. The results of this study may help employees in a University to comprehend their experiences at work. This study also may provide relevant information to policy-making bodies in regards to the well-being of workers in a university. Furthermore, the study may supply some information that might be useful for a social scientist who deals with work experiences.

The Framework of the Study

The negative impact of workplace and work experiences can be a source of dissatisfaction and stress. However, stress from the workplace can be managed by determining its causes (Michie, 2002). Senreich and colleagues (2020) stated that several factors impact the compassion satisfaction of workers. These factors might influence their work experience which might cause unproductive and inefficient in their respective job assignment (Barber et al., 2020; Tissenbaum, 2020; Tomczak & Jaśkowski, 2020). According to Johari and Jha (2020), workers must be motivated

and given incentives to become contented and productive in their work assignments. In the findings of Casinillo et al. (2021), awards and incentives for meritorious work performance must be provided by the management to increase the desire of an employee in accomplishing their given task. Another important factor of a negative work experience is the heavy workload (Yi et al., 2020). In the aspect of employees in a University, Griffith and Altinay (2020) mentioned that multiple teaching preparations and heavy loads have a negative impact on the productivity of a teacher and staff. Thus, institutional management policies must be considered to adjust based on their employees' productivity and effectiveness. Setiadi and colleagues (2020) found out that the educational attainment, age composition, and work experience of employees have a momentous influence on their productivity. The level of education increases the knowledge of workers and influences their attitudes, which makes them more competitive in their work (Capricho et al., 2021). Leisure activities are also part of the picture. Leisure at work can provide intrinsic satisfaction or enjoyment, relaxation, and intimacy to their co-workers (Tinsley et al., 1993). Moreover, it is stated in the study of Bustillo et al. (2021) that health feature is very important to be assessed especially for older worker. Health is a strong determinant of satisfaction and well-being at work according to the findings of Casinillo et al. (2020) and Fekete et al. (2020). Hence, the framework of this study elucidates the work experiences of employees concerning their different socioeconomic data that influence labor productivity.

2. METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study was descriptive-correlational. Similar to the study of Casinillo & Casinillo (2021), we used quantitative survey data to understand the perception of employees' experiences and capture its influencing predictors at Visayas State University, Philippines. The study utilized some descriptive measures and inferential statistical methods in summarizing and predicting the data, respectively. The participants of this study are bonafide employees of Visayas State University, Leyte, Philippines. This study, utilized secondary data from the current study of Casinillo et al. (2021) entitled "Economics of Happiness: A Social Study on Determinants of Well-Being among Employees in a State University."

The study dealt with the well-being of employees in a State University in regards to the different influencing factors. However, the study is only limited to subjective well-being and does not tackle the perception of the employees'

experiences at work. Hence, the study considered the different experiences such as "Routinely (scale of 1 to 10)", "Creative (scale of 1 to 10)", "Challenging (scale of 1 to 10)", "Enjoyable" (scale of 1 to 10)", "Logical (scale of 1 to 10)", and "Rewarding (scale of 1 to 10)" as dependent variables (response variables). Table 1 shows the mean interval that perception scores will possibly fall and its corresponding interpretation (Casinillo & Casinillo, 2021).

Table 1. Mean interval of perception scores and its interpretation

Mean Interval of Perception Scores	Interpretation
1.00 – 2.80	Very unsatisfied
2.81 – 4.60	Unsatisfied
4.61 – 6.40	Neutral
6.41 – 8.20	Satisfied
8.21 – 10.00	Very satisfied

For the independent variables (predictors), the study dealt with the following: nature of work (1-teaching or 0-non-teaching), age (in years), sex (1-male or 0-female), civil status (1-married or 0-not married), hometown (1-urban or 0-rural), educational attainment (1-bachelors degree, 2-masters level, 3-masters degree, 4-doctoral level, 5-doctoral degree), years in service, job status (1-permanent or 0-non permanent), and net income (in peso). Moreover, the following 10-item scale questions regarding the University's administration were also included such as fair administration (scale of 1 to 10), opportunities for promotion (scale of 1 to 10), bonuses (scale of 1 to 10), rewards, and recognition (scale of 1 to 10), and overtime pay (scale of 1 to 10). The implications of the 10-point Likert scale are as follows: 1-very unsatisfied to 10-very satisfied. As for the dependent variable, it has undergone a reliability test and found that the instrument was reliable since it generated a Cronbach alpha (Cronbach, 1951) of 0.73.

The selected secondary data has undergone a clearing procedure where extreme values (outliers) were excluded from the analysis. Hence, the study employed 159 employees (99 teaching faculties and 60 non-teaching staff) as participants. For the data calculation and extraction, this study used descriptive statistics such as minimum value, maximum value, mean (\bar{x}), standard deviation (s), and coefficient of variation ($C.V.$). The basis for interpreting $C.V.$ is the study of Casinillo and Guarte (2018) in which it is stated that a consistent response has at most a 10% coefficient of variation.

Additionally, multiple linear regression models were constructed to determine the possible significant factors that might influence the employees' work experiences (dependent variables). Before interpreting the regression results, the model has undergone diagnostic tests such as the homoscedasticity test (Breusch-Pagan Test), omitted variable test (Ramsey RESET test), multicollinearity test (Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)), and normality test (Shapiro-Wilk W test and Kernel density estimate graphs) to ensure the adequacy and validate its prediction. The advantage of the analysis is that it can capture possible factors that might influence the work experiences of the VSU employees, however, it is just limited to the variables considered in the model. Furthermore, all calculations in the data analysis were done using STATA version 14.0.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Dominantly, about 62% of the employees in VSU are faculty (instructors/professors) and 38% are administrative staff who are assigned to non-teaching work. Employees' age is close to 39 years old and there are more female (64%) workers than male (36%). Additionally, more than half of the employees at VSU are married (58%). In regards to employees' hometowns, on average, 26% of them live in urban places and 74% live in rural places. On average, employees of VSU are mostly master's degrees and have almost 13 years in service. About 57% of the employees have permanent status and 43% are contractual or renewable status. Approximately, the monthly net income of employees is closed to PHP 22512.58. The employees have rated the administration as fairly satisfied ($\bar{x} = 7.55, s = 2.19$) where they are comfortable with the rules and regulations in the University. As for opportunities for promotion, employees are also satisfied ($\bar{x} = 7.21, s = 2.60$) with their experience in the University. Regarding the University incentives, employees rated the bonuses ($\bar{x} = 7.91, s = 3.33$) and awards ($\bar{x} = 6.89, s = 2.92$) aspect of the University as satisfied. However, employees are not satisfied ($\bar{x} = 4.27, s = 3.28$) with the aspect of overtime pay in the University.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for teachers' socio-economic profile.

Variables	$\bar{x} \pm s$	min	max
Teaching (dummy)	0.62±0.49	0	1
Age (in years)	38.87±12.82	22	71
Male (dummy)	0.36±0.48	0	1
Married (dummy)	0.58±0.49	0	1
Urban (dummy)	0.26±0.44	0	1
Educational attainment ^a	2.61±1.55	1	5
Years in service	12.56±12.05	0.25	45
Permanent (dummy)	0.57±0.49	0	1
Monthly Net Income ^b	22512.58±21404.87	5000	219000
Fair administration ^c	7.55±2.19	1	10
Opportunity for promotion ^c	7.21±2.60	1	10
Bonuses ^c	7.91±3.33	1	10
Awards ^c	6.89±2.92	1	10
Over time pay ^c	4.27±3.28	1	10

Note: a - (1.00-1.80-bachelors degree, 1.81-2.60-masters level, 2.61-3.40-masters degree, 3.41-4.20-doctorals level, 4.21-5.00-doctoral degree)

b - Philippine Peso.

c - Scale 1 to 10.

Work Experiences among Employees

On average, employees in VSU were "satisfied" with the routines ($\bar{x} = 7.00, s = 2.61$) of their respective work assignments (Table 3). This suggests that employees are following procedures so that they may be productive and efficient in their daily tasks. It involves a work pattern and assigned function in each unit to obtain the institution's goals and objectives (Wilson, 2016). The coefficient of variation reveals that the perception of employees is not consistent ($C.V. = 37.29\%$) which indicates that employees are possibly assigned different jobs over time. In that case, it is suggested that there is the possibility that employees are having a baffling experience in establishing a daily routine plan. Table 3 also reveals that employees were "satisfied" with the creativity ($\bar{x} = 7.89, s = 1.45$) that they have experience in their job. In that case, employees are learning new ideas through a creative way of doing things. Employees' creativity allows for solving problems with open-mindedness and resilience which results in productive and efficient behavior (Gordon, 2020; Runco & Beghetto, 2019).

According to the employees, working at a University is challenging ($\bar{x} = 7.89, s = 1.45$), and rated as "very satisfied" (Table 3). This implies that employees

are experiencing some difficulties in doing their job due to the volume of paper works nowadays. Casinillo and colleagues (2021) reveal that there is an increasing demand for paper documents in universities to achieve transparency and detailed proof. Even in the academe, there are additional paper works to be submitted by the faculties aside from the teaching workloads. In the study of Carette et al. (2013), it is stated that challenging work assignment can influence their performance. In that case, it is suggested that work assignments must be properly distributed based on the employees' capability. However, employees are enjoying ($\bar{x} = 8.08, s = 1.75$) their jobs and are rated as "satisfied" (Table 3). This means that employees are feeling good and satisfied with their respective work assignments. It further implies that employees are contented and satisfied serving the university accompanied by the benefits they can get from their job while learning various skills and expertise (Marbán et al., 2021; Keena et al., 2020). Additionally, employees are also enjoying the company of their colleagues in which they learn from others' experiences and ideas (Wagner et al., 2016). Moreover, employees are satisfied with how logical ($\bar{x} = 8.17, s = 1.65$) their respective jobs in the university. The job assignment allows their critical thinking work which is a good brain exercise. Using reasoning in jobs will make them active and refrain them from boredom. This result is parallel to the findings of Casinillo and Casinillo (2021) which also deal with the experiences of educators.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for work experiences among employees.

Work Experiences	$\bar{x} \pm s$	C. V. (%)	Description^b
Routinely ^a	7.00±2.61	37.29	Satisfied
Creative ^a	7.89±1.45	18.38	Satisfied
Challenging ^a	8.53±1.46	17.12	Very satisfied
Enjoyable ^a	8.08±1.75	21.66	Satisfied
Logical ^a	8.17±1.65	20.19	Satisfied
Rewarding ^a	7.57±1.95	25.76	Satisfied
Over-all Perception	7.87±1.81	22.99	Satisfied

Note: a - Scale 1 to 10.

b - See Table 1 for details.

Working in a university is quite challenging but rewarding ($\bar{x} = 7.57, s = 1.95$) as shown in Table 3. It can be gleaned that employees are "satisfied" with their job and express a sign of achievement. This result supports the findings of Casinillo and Casinillo (2021) who state that educators that are feeling good and satisfied with their jobs have a possibility to have a good psychological state of

mind. On average, overall results reveals that employees are satisfied ($\bar{x} = 7.87, s = 1.81$) with their respective jobs at the university (Table 3). This implies that working at a university is satisfying experience and rewarding. The coefficient of variation reveals that employees' perception is somehow consistent which only shows a 23% of relative variability. In that case, there is a strong probability that employees in the university are consistently working with dedication and passion.

Regression Models

The six regression models as work experiences such as routinely, creative, challenging, enjoyable, logical, and rewarding are regressands are shown in Table 4. By the Breusch-Pagan test, it is discovered that the models had no issues in their variances, that is, the p-value is greater than 0.05, and accepted the null hypothesis that the variances are homogeneous. Models I and II have no omitted variable bias (p-values are greater than 0.05) and models III, IV, V, and VI have omitted variable bias (p-values are lesser than 0.05) by the Ramsey RESET test. Additionally, it is suggested by Allison (2012) that the models are safe from multicollinearity problems if and only if the variance inflation factor (VIF) is less than 10. Hence, the 6 models had no problem with multicollinearity since the condition $VIF < 10$ is satisfied which implies that no correlation exists between the pairwise independent variables. With the aid of the Shapiro-Wilk W test, it is found that the residuals of the six models are not normal (p-values are lesser than 0.05), however, by Kernel density estimate graphs, it is shown that the residuals of these models are almost normal in nature. The five regression models (I, II, IV, V, and VI) are significant at a 1% level, which implies that there are factors that significantly influence the work experiences of employees. As for model III, it is not significant even at most 10% level, which suggests that few significant predictors exist in the model. Moreover, the 6 models' coefficient of determination or goodness-of-fit ($R^2 > 0.15$) shows that it has fitted the information sets which implies that it can predict significant factors of the employees' perception scores of their work experiences.

Table 4 reveals that an instructor/professor has experienced a logical procedure in their work and it is significant at a 10% level. This implies that a teaching job requires more reasoning and higher-order thinking skills compared to administrative work. Being a teacher is not that easy since it requires higher educational attainment and good academic skills to impart information to students. In the study of Casinillo and Casinillo (2021), it is stated that being a good teacher, requires time management and proper training to become a globally competitive educator. In that case, more logic and reasoning are involved in the

teaching job as opposed to administrative work. Model IV reveals that male employees are more likely to enjoy their job in the university and it is significant at a 10% level (Table 4). Result suggests that male employees are feeling good and experience pleasure in their respective job compared to female employees. In fact, working in a university is not that exhausting and tiring even if it is challenging unlike any other male job outside the institution. However, this finding is not consistent with some existing studies in the literature which stated that male workers have lower work-related satisfaction and well-being (Wharton & Baron, 1987; Clark, 1997).

In Model II, it is revealed that married employees tend to be creative in their job at a 1% level of significance (Table 4). In fact, married employees are more mature concerning the decision-making process and creating new ideas despite work pressure. Reddy and colleagues (2010) stated that married employees tend to adopt a work-life balance to have a positive experience at work and creatively solve existing conflicts in their workplace and home. Moreover, married employees are motivated to work because they are positively influenced by their family members (Choung & Lee, 2007). The model I shows that employees with lower educational attainment are more likely to adopt a routine and it is significant at a 10% level (Table 4). As new workers, they tend to follow a procedural process to achieve their goals. Casinillo and Casinillo (2021) suggested that familiarization with daily work plans or routines can be a positive learning experience and may develop a time management process. As for old workers, routine activities may not be necessary since they are already equipped and experienced in the daily work-related scenario. According to Wagner et al. (2020), following a routine or schedule of activities for work-related can be boring and can cause sometimes a stress disorder.

Monthly income is a significant independent variable for both model IV (at a 10% level) and VI (at a 5% level) (Table 4). The result implies that income is an influencing factor that positively affects the enjoyment of employees in a University. Additionally, income is also a predictor of how rewarding is their job assignment. In fact, income is the main reason why employees are working and further implies that it is a motivator despite challenges encountered. In that case, employees are highly satisfied with their job if they are equally compensated for their job experiences. Although income has a slight influence on the happiness of employees (Kollamparambil, 2020; Lim et al., 2020; Casinillo et al., 2021), still it is a predictor of how enjoyable and rewarding their work is at the University. This suggests that increasing employees' income, results in enjoyable, productive, and

efficient workers. In addition, fair administration is a significant determinant of how routinely (at a 10% level), enjoyable (at a 5% level), logical (at a 5% level), and rewarding (at a 1% level) their job in the university (Table 4). In the study of Casinillo et al. (2021), it is stated that fair administration is very crucial in improving employees' trust, well-being, and retention. In that case, the employer must deal with the employees' work concerns with fairness and no partiality.

Likewise, opportunities for promotion are a significant determinant of employees' work experiences such as creative (at a 10% level), challenging (at a 5% level), enjoyable (at a 5% level), and rewarding (at a 10% level) (Table 4). Result suggests that if employees are subject to promotion or higher rank (opportunities for a higher salary), then they are more likely motivated to work despite the challenges. This result is consistent with the finding of Casinillo et al. (2020) that promotion to a higher rank increases employees' happiness as well as work satisfaction. Moreover, awards (at a 10% level) or incentives are a significant factor in how logical their respective work in the university is (Table 4). This suggests that employees believe that it is logical and deserving to have an award or incentives for meritorious performance in the university. Hence, it follows that, on average, employees are doing some meritorious performance to achieve the university's standard of acquiring awards. In fact, Yeung et al. (2020) stated that awards and incentives are a contributor to leveling up the workers' knowledge, essential skills, and competitive and productive nature. Furthermore, Table 4 revealed that overtime pay is a significant determinant of how rewarding (at a 10% level) the employees' jobs at the university. This implies that employees are willing to work beyond the allotted time as long as they are paid beyond what they are paid for (Casinillo et al., 2021). Extra income is a great help, especially for employees with low income.

Table 4. Multiple regression models for work experiences and their influencing factors.

Independent Variables	Dependent variables (Multiple Regression Models)					
	Routinely ^b (I)	Creative ^b (II)	Challenging ^b (III)	Enjoyable ^b (IV)	Logical ^b (V)	Rewarding ^b (VI)
Teaching (dummy)	-0.4923 ^{ns} (0.6544)	0.3839 ^{ns} (0.3736)	0.3770 ^{ns} (0.0342)	0.0259 ^{ns} (0.4228)	0.5654* (0.3419)	-0.2211 ^{ns} (0.4319)
Age (in years)	0.0083 ^{ns} (0.0296)	0.0016 ^{ns} (0.0188)	0.0150 ^{ns} (0.0179)	-0.0009 ^{ns} (0.0191)	-0.0150 ^{ns} (0.0199)	-0.0139 ^{ns} (0.0226)
Male (dummy)	0.3970 ^{ns} (0.4272)	0.1899 ^{ns} (0.2450)	-0.2774 ^{ns} (0.2233)	0.4995* (0.2760)	-0.1264 ^{ns} (0.2736)	-0.1698 ^{ns} (0.2925)
Married (dummy)	0.4336 ^{ns} (0.4708)	0.8489*** (0.2952)	0.3866 ^{ns} (0.3124)	0.3425 ^{ns} (0.3042)	0.3844 ^{ns} (0.2926)	0.0043 ^{ns} (0.3025)
Urban (dummy)	-0.2126 ^{ns} (0.4759)	0.0131 ^{ns} (0.2721)	-0.0181 ^{ns} (0.2960)	0.0095 ^{ns} (0.3075)	0.0024 ^{ns} (0.3276)	-0.2180 ^{ns} (0.3253)
Educational ^a attainment	-0.3842* (0.2221)	-0.1829 ^{ns} (0.1269)	-0.1213 ^{ns} (0.1084)	-0.2242 ^{ns} (0.1435)	-0.0817 ^{ns} (0.1034)	-0.1899 ^{ns} (0.1553)
Years in service	0.0041 ^{ns} (0.0271)	-0.0212 ^{ns} (0.0161)	-0.0046 ^{ns} (0.0144)	-0.0137 ^{ns} (0.0175)	-0.0241 ^{ns} (0.0174)	0.0050 ^{ns} (0.0204)
Permanent (dummy)	-0.0891 ^{ns} (0.5914)	-0.0197 ^{ns} (0.4076)	-0.4369 ^{ns} (0.4414)	-0.2569 ^{ns} (0.3821)	-0.2312 ^{ns} (0.4231)	0.2643 ^{ns} (0.4348)
Monthly Net ^b Income	-0.00001 ^{ns} (0.00001)	1.91e-06 ^{ns} (4.55e-06)	1.81e-06 ^{ns} (4.68e-06)	0.00001* (7.18e-06)	6.09e-06 ^{ns} (3.89e-06)	0.00001** (4.99e-06)
Fair administration ^c	0.1972* (0.1180)	0.0451 ^{ns} (0.0886)	0.0623 ^{ns} (0.0874)	0.1568** (0.0762)	0.2513** (0.0992)	0.2994*** (0.1036)
Opportunity ^c for promotion	0.0613 ^{ns} (0.1055)	0.1084* (0.0595)	0.1619** (0.0676)	0.1670** (0.0682)	-0.0016 ^{ns} (0.0671)	0.1590* (0.0817)
Bonuses ^c	0.0628 ^{ns} (0.0988)	0.0279 ^{ns} (0.0642)	0.0187 ^{ns} (0.0660)	-0.0479 ^{ns} (0.0639)	0.0138 ^{ns} (0.0775)	0.00005 ^{ns} (0.0781)
Awards ^c	-0.0827 ^{ns} (0.1037)	-0.0575 ^{ns} (0.0592)	-0.0233 ^{ns} (0.0593)	0.0526 ^{ns} (0.0670)	0.1198* (0.0699)	0.0476 ^{ns} (0.0777)
Over time pay ^c	0.0751 ^{ns} (0.0651)	0.0435 ^{ns} (0.0360)	0.0436 ^{ns} (0.0339)	0.0201 ^{ns} (0.0421)	-0.0591 ^{ns} (0.0426)	0.0757* (0.0420)
Constant	5.7026*** (1.1726)	6.5952*** (1.0182)	6.3588*** (0.9841)	5.8503*** (0.7576)	6.1619*** (0.9841)	4.3494*** (0.9928)
No. of Participants	159	159	159	159	159	159
F_{computed}	2.46	2.86	1.54	3.45	3.21	4.42
p-value	0.0038	0.0008	0.1028	0.0001	0.0002	<0.0001
R² (Goodness of fit)	0.1933	0.1584	0.1721	0.2513	0.2438	0.3401

Note: a - (1.00-1.80-bachelors degree, 1.81-2.60-masters level, 2.61-3.40-masters degree, 3.41-4.20-doctorals level, 4.21-5.00-doctoral degree); b - Philippine Peso ; c - Scale 1 to 10.

Standard errors are enclosed in parentheses.

ns- not significant; * - significant at 10% level; ** - significant at 5% level; *** - significant at 1% level.

4. CONCLUSION

The study's main objective is to investigate the VSU employees' work experiences and their determinants. The results of this current study have revealed that working at the university is a challenging experience, however, employees are feeling satisfied with how routinely, creative, enjoyable, logical, and rewarding is their respective job assignments. Using the regression models, it is concluded that the teaching job is more logical compared to the administrative assignment. Additionally, results have shown that male workers are more likely to enjoy their work compared to female employees in the university. And employees with lower educational attainment are pursuing a routine or procedure in accomplishing their job. Moreover, it is concluded that monthly income, fair administration, opportunities for promotion, and awards are positively influencing the employees' work experiences. This suggests that the benefits of working at the University are determinants of being a productive and efficient worker. Results also revealed that to make the work in a university rewarding, overtime pay must be given to employees for their extra work beyond the government time. Thus, to improve employees' well-being, the university may provide incentives, benefits, and financial compensation for their excess work service. Plus recognition or awards must be provided for meritorious performance of employees to motivate them in doing their best and to attain a favorable work experience. It is recommended that leisure and health activities must also be implemented to help workers cope with stress. Furthermore, this research paper recommends incorporating employees' economic variables and students' perspectives on online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic for future studies to assess the efficacy and fill the limitation of the current study.

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